

California sends millions of dollars out of state for carbon offsets of dubious quality

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California sends approximately \$140 million out of state each year for carbon offsets, most of which have little-to-no actual climate benefit. As the state considers extending its cap-and-trade program to 2045, lawmakers have the opportunity to replace the current offset program with a program that works for California and for the climate. We review alternatives to the current program, and find that Oregon’s Community Climate Investment program provides a model that California should consider. Instead of offsetting, Oregon allows businesses covered under its cap-and-trade program to pay into a fund focused on reducing emissions in the state while improving air quality and energy affordability in low-income and Tribal communities. California could choose a fund structure that avoids increasing energy prices for lower-income residents.

In this brief, we outline:

1. The size and significance of offsets in California’s cap-and-trade program;
2. The share of credits that come from out-of-state projects;
3. Why so many credits from out-of-state projects have been eligible under ARB;
4. Why most of these credits have little-to-no actual climate benefit; and
5. Avenues for policymakers to reform and improve the offset program while keeping funds in state, supporting decarbonization, and reducing energy costs for lower-income Californians.

California’s offset program is a large part of its cap-and-trade program. California’s cap-and-trade program puts a declining cap on approximately 80% of California emissions.¹ Regulated emitters (e.g., electrical utilities and fuel providers) are allowed to purchase offset credits — each meant to

¹ <https://ww2.arb.ca.gov/our-work/programs/cap-and-trade-program/about>

represent one ton of avoided CO₂ emissions — instead of reducing their own emissions, for up to 4% of their total emissions (increasing to 6% in 2026). This essentially increases the “cap” on total emissions by the amount of offsets used. Eligible offset credits come from five approved project types and projects can be located anywhere in the United States (see Figure 1). The California Air Resources Board (ARB) estimated that from 2021 to 2030, **California’s maximum offset limit will add credits to the cap-and-trade program equal to 22% of total expected reductions in the state in that period, and equal to half of the expected effect of the cap-and-trade program itself on emissions.**²

Two-thirds of offset credits retired in California’s 2021-23 compliance period were from out-of-state projects. During the previous cap-and-trade reauthorization in 2017, California cut the size of the offset program in half, from 8% of capped emissions to 4%. Legislators also required half of all offsets used to have “direct environmental benefits in the state” (DEBS). These provisions were implemented in response to environmental justice concerns that carbon offsets allowed California polluters to continue to emit greenhouse gases alongside toxic pollutants that were disproportionately affecting the health of lower-income populations.

Despite these reforms, two-thirds of the offset credits used for the 2021-23 compliance period were sourced from out-of-state projects. This is because **many offset projects from elsewhere in the country have been able to meet California’s lenient definition of providing “direct environmental benefits in the state.”** Most out-of-state offset projects considered to have DEBS create offset credits by destroying potent climate-heating refrigerant gases in Arkansas, Illinois, and other states with specialized facilities. ARB considers these refrigerant destruction projects to have DEBS if any refrigerants were sourced from within California, thus preventing the release of those gases in the state.³ However, most DEBS refrigerant projects contain very little material that is actually sourced from within California. It is common for projects to destroy refrigerants sourced from over ten states across the country, and most only including a single California source.

Our analysis further reveals that California is spending roughly \$140 million annually on offsets from out-of-state projects.⁴

Most California offset credits do not represent real emissions reductions. The highly exaggerated climate benefits that we see with California’s forest and manure methane digester⁵ offset

² Haya, B. K. (2018). Fact sheet: *The size of California’s carbon offset program*. University of California, Berkeley. <https://gspp.berkeley.edu/assets/uploads/page/FACTSHEET-the-size-of-CAs-offset-program-Haya.pdf>

³ <https://ww2.arb.ca.gov/our-work/programs/compliance-offset-program/direct-environmental-benefits>

⁴ Calculated by multiplying the 26 million credits used by emitters to meet the 2021-23 compliance period (see [ARB Offset Credit Issuance table](#) with average offset prices during 2022-24 for DEBS credits (\$26) and non-DEBS credits (\$17) (see [ARB’s annual summary of market transfers reports](#)).

⁵ Pierce, M. H., & Strong, A. L. (2023). An evaluation of New York state livestock carbon offset projects under California’s cap and trade program. *Carbon Management*, 2211946. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17583004.2023.2211946>

protocols have been documented under most major carbon offset programs.⁶ Poor offset quality (i.e., projects that claim more credits than achieved emissions reductions) is an inherent challenge to carbon offsetting because of the market’s structure.⁷ All market actors benefit from excess crediting, including the project developers, the credit users, and the third-party auditors hired directly by the project developers. At the same time, offset quality depends on complex quantification methods that are often highly uncertain, in part because impacts must be measured against a counterfactual scenario that never actually happens. Uncertainty causes information asymmetries, whereby project developers know more about what they would have done otherwise than the regulators and auditors, causing adverse selection, since those developers that need to make the least change to generate credits have the greatest incentive to participate, depressing prices. It is this combination — market actors with aligned interests making quantification decisions in the context of significant complexity and uncertainty — that has led to such high levels of over-crediting across all major offset programs to date.

Figure 1: ARB credits issued to date

Source: [ARB Offset Credit Issuance Table](#)

Three-quarters of offset credits issued to date under California’s offset program are from improved forest management projects. Improved forest management offset projects pay forestland owners in the United States to increase the amount of carbon in their forests compared to their management practice without the offset income. Most participating landowners claim that without the ability to sell offset credits, they would rapidly harvest their forests to sell timber, significantly reducing the amount of carbon in their forests. The more timber they claim they would have harvested in a no-offsets counterfactual, the more credits are issued.

Studies of ARB improved forest management offset projects found that the landowners were unlikely to have degraded their forests, and found no discernible impact of the offset project on land management practices compared to past management on the participating lands, or compared to similar parcels in the region.^{8,9} Other studies found that the ARB protocol significantly underestimates

⁶ See our [Repository of Article on Offset Quality](#) for summaries of literature by project type, and our discussion on the underlying structural reasons for poor quality offset programs below.

⁷ Giles, C. (2023). *What carbon credits tell us about why environmental programs fail*. The Regulatory Review, Penn Program on Regulation. <https://www.theregreview.org/2023/12/18/giles-what-carbon-offsets-tell-us-about-why-environmental-programs-fail/>

⁸ Coffield, S. R., Vo, C. D., Wang, J. A., Badgley, G., Goulden, M. L., Cullenward, D., Anderegg, W. R. L., & Randerson, J. T. (2022). Using remote sensing to quantify the additional climate benefits of California forest carbon offset projects. *Global Change Biology*, gcb.16380. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16380>

⁹ Stapp, J., Nolte, C., Potts, M., Baumann, M., Haya, B. K., & Butsic, V. (2023). Little evidence of management change in California’s forest offset program. *Nature Communications Earth & Environment*. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s43247-023-00984-2>

emissions from timber harvesting that shifts elsewhere due to reduced harvesting on project sites,¹⁰ and underestimates the risk of reversal from fire and other disturbances.¹¹ Another study found that the protocol created incentives to increase carbon on lands that were otherwise targeted by the state for fuels reduction, putting the offset program at direct odds with the goals of California’s Forest Health program.^{12,13}

Policy Alternatives

Create a contributions-style community investment fund for high-impact climate justice investments — the Oregon approach. (Recommended)

Similar to Oregon’s “[Community Climate Investment](#)” program,¹⁴ California could replace its offset program with one that allows entities to pay into a fund that supports emissions reductions and environmental justice co-benefits in the state. Such a fund could be structured in many ways; Oregon’s program provides one good model. In Oregon, emitters regulated under the state’s cap-and-trade program can purchase credits through a centralized state authority, which directs money to one or several nonprofit organizations. These organizations are responsible for designing programs, subject to approval by Oregon’s Equity Advisory Committee, to be designed and implemented by communities, nonprofit organizations, and other groups, to reduce emissions in the state’s transportation, residential, commercial, and industrial sectors. Programs should focus on activities that benefit the state’s underserved communities, with 15% of funds allocated to Tribal communities. Regulated entities can use the credits to cover 20% of their total emissions (as opposed to California’s 4%), and the credits cannot be traded or resold. The program is expected to be operational by the end of 2026.

The cost of a credit under Oregon’s program is derived from the expected cost of reducing or removing 1tCO₂e. In 2025, this is \$132¹⁵ — several times more expensive than the price of ARB offsets.

¹⁰ Haya, B. K., Evans, S., Brown, L., Bukoski, J., Butsic, V., Cabiyo, B., Jacobson, R., Kerr, A., Potts, M., & Sanchez, D. L. (2023). Comprehensive review of carbon quantification by improved forest management offset protocols. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, 6, 958879. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2023.958879>

¹¹ Badgley, G., Chay, F., Chegwidden, O. S., Hamman, J. J., Freeman, J., and Cullenward, D. (2022). California’s forest carbon offsets buffer pool is severely undercapitalized. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change* (5). <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2022.930426>

¹² Herbert, C., Haya, B. K., Stephens, S. L., & Butsic, V. (2022). Managing nature-based solutions in fire-prone ecosystems: Competing management objectives in California forests evaluated at a landscape scale. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, 5, 957189. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2022.957189>

¹³ Please find a longer summary literature in the [IFM section of our Repository of Articles on Offset Quality](#).

¹⁴ For more details on the program, please see the adopted rule starting on page 72: [https://www.oregon.gov/deq/rulemaking/Pages/ CPP2024.aspx](https://www.oregon.gov/deq/rulemaking/Pages/_CPP2024.aspx)

¹⁵ <https://www.oregon.gov/deq/ghgp/Documents/CCIContributionAmounts.pdf>

In California, lawmakers could ensure that the money raised from such a program directly addresses energy affordability issues in lower-income communities. In addition, lawmakers could set a lower price for such credits, even to the point of matching current ARB offset credit costs, thereby preventing any increase in total costs to covered entities.¹⁶

Require all offset credits to be in state or to have DEBS — the Washington approach. (Not recommended)

California could require all offsets to be from projects in the state, or to deliver DEBS as Washington’s “[Cap-and-Invest](#)” program does. This reform would not address the underlying issues of offsets failing to deliver their stated climate benefit, and would limit the funding to predefined project types defined by carbon accounting protocols. Further, if all projects must have DEBS, the program could still allow for dubious claims of environmental benefits as we discussed above.

Attempt to improve offset quality. (Not recommended)

Lawmakers might try to improve offset integrity by limiting eligible projects to those with highly rigorous standards for integrity. But this would require succeeding where all major voluntary and compliance efforts have failed.

Because the hurdles to successfully deploying high-integrity credits are so high, it may be practically impossible to improve integrity issues to a satisfactory threshold. Any effort to improve quality must start with taking conflicts of interest out of the system. This involves (1) a truly independent body with the interdisciplinary scientific expertise to evaluate protocols against clear criteria,¹⁷ (2) an independent verification system whereby verifiers are hired by an independent body whose mandate is credit quality rather than by project developers, (3) transparent credit calculations and assumptions so independent parties can assess quality, and (4) a nimble program where protocols are updated as new research is published. These elements are each necessary to address the structural quality challenges, but might still not be sufficient given them.

Limit offset use. (Not recommended)

California could explicitly limit the use of offsets under the cap-and-trade program by extending the current 4% limit, or by reducing it. This would reduce exposure to dubious offsets and money being spent out-of-state. However, this would limit funding for high-impact climate justice projects.

Straight reauthorization. (Strongly not recommended)

¹⁶ Setting the price below the expected “marginal abatement cost” would mean that credits would not fully balance out pollution from covered entities; still, the expected climate impact would potentially be greater than the benefit from having the same money spent on low-quality offsets.

¹⁷ See for example the criteria described here: <https://gspp.berkeley.edu/research-and-impact/centers/cepp/projects/berkeley-carbon-trading-project/developing-ucs-offset-strategy#methods>

A straight reauthorization of California's cap-and-trade program is the least preferred option. It would not improve program effectiveness or prevent funds from flowing out of state, and could even allow for the size of the offset program to expand under pressure from regulated emitters.

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